

NUTRITIONAL STATUS AFFECTS SERUM INTERLEUKIN-8 LEVEL IN ACTIVE PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS AND LATENT TUBERCULOSIS PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Tuberculosis (TB) is a significant health problem. Someone infected by Mtb may become latent TB or active TB. Interleukin-8 (IL-8) is proinflammatory cytokine as well as a chemokine which play a role in immunity of Mtb. Furthermore, the progressivity of Mtb is also correlated with ageing, diabetes mellitus (DM), and nutritional states. Nowadays, there is only a limited study from Indonesia focusing on IL-8 level in infected Mtb patients. Studies on the role of factors affecting the correlation between IL-8 and Mtb infection are also still limited. **Objective:** This study aimed to determine serum IL-8 levels and also its association with age, DM, and nutritional status in active lung TB and latent TB. **Methods:** It was an analytic study with a cross-sectional design. Samples were the serum of latent TB and active lung TB patients, which were examined their IL-8 levels with ELISA analysis. The study was conducted in Wahidin Sudirohusodo teaching hospital and its networks in June 2015 until July 2015. **Results:** IL-8 levels were higher in latent TB (6636,1pg/mL) than inactive TB group (2760,5 pg/mL). From the multivariate analysis, the IL-8 level was inseparable to nutritional status in both active and latent TB. Statistically, the role of these two variables were 54,1%. In underweight group, mean of IL-8 level in latent TB were higher (7047 pg/mL) than active TB group (2066,66 pg/mL), but no significant difference statistically ($p>0,05$). Within the non-underweight group, we found a significant difference between IL-8 inactive TB (3364 pg/mL) and latent TB (1749,1 pg/mL). **Conclusion:** IL-8 levels were significantly higher in latent TB than active lung TB, and this difference was affected by nutritional status.

KEYWORDS Interleukin-8, Active Lung Tuberculosis, Latent Tuberculosis

Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) is a significant health problem worldwide for causing a high mortality rate among infectious diseases.[1] Data

from the World Health Organization in 2012 reported around 9 million new cases and 1,5 million people died of TB. Indonesia is at the 5th rank country with most TB incidence worldwide, reaching 410.000 to 520.000 cases.[2]

Tuberculosis is an infection caused by Mycobacterium tuberculosis (Mtb), spread through the respiratory tract.[3] About 5 to 10 percent of infected people eventually becoming active TB, and the remaining would go probably without symptoms or even becoming latent TB. Only about 10% of the infected can maintain the total elimination of Mtb due to proper immune function.[4,5,6] In the United States, studies on active TB households showed about 20-30% of them ended as latent, and only

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1% became active TB. [5]

Active TB is an infection caused by Mtb with the presentation of symptoms. Symptoms can either general or specific for pulmonary TB infection such as chest pain, prolonged cough (more than three weeks), and hemoptysis (bloody cough).[6] Latent TB defined as an infection caused by non-replicated macrophagous Mtb, but can eventually present as an active TB in the distorted immune response. Progression from latent to active TB needs activation of Mtb. Some factors can trigger the progressivity of the disease to present an active form, usually involving a decrease in the immune system. [7]

Recently, we know two common groups of cytokines in the immune response process to Mtb; proinflammatory cytokines and anti-inflammatory cytokines. Some pro-inflammatory cytokines involved in TB infection are TNF- α , interleukin (IL)-1 β , IL-6, IL-12, IL-8, IL-15 and IFN- γ . In the group anti-inflammatory cytokines, there are IL-10, tumour growth factor (TGF)- β and IL-4. Proinflammatory cytokines play a role in granuloma forming to maintain infection and prevent advance infection from spreading elsewhere. Conversely, anti-inflammatory cytokines can decrease immune responses to Mtb, causing inhibition of rising inflammatory responses. In the release of exceeded antiinflammatory cytokines, failure of controlling Mtb infection may happen, enabling the infection to widely spread and becoming active TB. Some chemokines also involved in the process of the immune response to Mtb like IL-8 and monocyte chemoattractant protein-1(MCP-1).[8,9]

Interleukin-8 is an amino acid polypeptide with an excellent ability to activate neutrophils and also has the chemotactic ability. Interleukin-8 produced by monocyte/macrophage, fibroblast cell, epithelial cell, and mast cell as a response to an exogenous or endogenous stimulus. Interleukin-8 had been proved to be involved in the immune process of Mtb infection, activating tissue inflammation and granuloma formation. As chemokine, IL-8 plays an essential role in attracting T-lymphocyte into TB granuloma formation and controlling cellular influx into Mtb location. As more and more Mtb bacilli involved in infection, IL-8 level hypothetically would increase.[10,11]

Bacterial growth is associated with some factors. [12] Malnutrition, Diabetes Mellitus (DM), and ageing would cause a decrease in the immune system, making the person more vulnerable to get infected.[13-19] The lower level of IL-8 found in malnutrition.14 Contrary, increasing level of IL-8 can be found in obesity.[15,16] Rising level of IL-8 generally found in DM patients.[17,18,19]

Examinations to directly diagnose latent TB has not been found yet. The presence of latent infection depends on immune response measurement as a substitute for the measurement of living bacteria. Recently, there are two latest diagnostic tools to detect latent TB; Quantiferon - TB Gold (QFT) and T-SPOT TB. Both known as interferon- γ -release assay (IGRA) for assessing the release of IFN- γ from a cell in vitro.[20]

Nowadays, there is only a limited study from Indonesia, focusing on IL-8 level in infected Mtb patients. Studies on the role of factors affecting the correlation between IL-8 and Mtb infection are also still limited. This study aimed to evaluate IL-8 level in infected Mtb patients as latent or active TB and assessing the role of related factors like age, nutritional status, and DM.

Material and Methods

Place and Time of Study

The study was conducted in Wahidin Sudirohusodo teaching-hospital and its network starting from June 2015 until July 2015.

Study Design and Variables

This was analytic with a cross-sectional approach study. Variables are independent (active TB and latent TB), dependent variable (IL-8 level), and confounding factors were age, DM and nutritional status.

Population and Sample

The population of study are both hospitalized or out-patients for TB in Wahidin Sudirohusodo teaching-hospital and its network, including all related households of active TB patients. Samples are population within inclusion criteria. Inclusions for latent TB is active TB households, without presenting any active TB symptoms and had a positive Quantiferon test result. While inclusions for active TB are presenting active TB symptoms, positive acid-fast bacilli sputum test, specific infiltrate for TB from Chest X-Ray, a new case of TB or consuming active TB regiments less than four weeks, without HIV coinfection.

Data Sampling Method

Data sampling was consecutive until the sample size reached.

Table 1 Study Sample Characteristics.

Sample Characteristics	n	%
Sex		
Male	26	47,3
Female	29	52,7
Age		
<=40 yo	25	45,5
>40 yo	30	54,5
Nutritional Status(BMI)		
Underweight	13	23,6
Non-underweight	42	76,4
Diabetes Melitus		
Present	6	10,9
Absent	49	89,1

Data Analysis

Data analysis using SPSS Statistics 22. Significant statistical value when $p < 0,05$. Data presented in narration, clarified by tables.

Results

The present study found from a total of 55 subjects, there were 20 active TB and 35 latent TB patients within inclusion criteria and approved informed consent.

The study population consisted 26 males (47.3%) and 29 females (52,7%). Age distribution were from 13-72 yo with mean

Table 2 Comparison of IL-8 level in active and latent TB.

TB	N	Mean IL-8 level	SD	P
Active TB	20	2760,5	3224,5	0,001
Latent TB	35	6636,1	1676,6	

Table 3 Multivariate Analysis of Confounding Factors in the Correlation between IL-8 level and pulmonary TB.

Step	Variables	Wald	P
Step 1	IL-8		11,074
		0,001	
	Age		0,648
		0,421	
	Nutritional Status		4,940
	0,026		
	DM		1,732
		0,188	
Step 2	IL-8		11,138
		0,001	
	Nutritional Status		4,989
		0,026	
	DM		2,398
		0,121	
Step 3	IL-8		11,778
		0,001	
	Nutritional Status		4,914
		0,027	

age 43,3±16,4 yo. Distribution of age group; 25 subjects (45,5%) age ≤ 40 yo and 30 subjects (54,5%) age > 40 yo. Based on nutritional status, there were 13 (23,6%) underweight subjects and 42 (76,4%) non underweight subjects (Table 1).

Data from table 2, found significant difference of IL-8 in active TB group from latent group (p<0,05). Mean IL-8 level were higher in latent TB group (6636,1pg/mL) compared to active TB group (2760,5pg/mL).

Three variables may play a role in the correlation between pulmonary TB and IL-8; age, nutritional status and DM. To control those factors, we performed a multivariate analysis. From table 3 result, remains two variables, IL-8 and BMI (p<0,01 and p<0,05). This shows that IL-8 is inseparable from nutritional status in the correlation with active TB and latent TB infection. Statistically, the role of these two variables were 54,1%.

Table 4 showed the role of nutritional status in the correlation between active TB infection and IL-8 level. In the underweight group, the mean level of IL-8 in latent TB was higher than the active TB group. Thus, statistically, there was no significant difference between IL-8 level inactive TB and latent TB (p>0,05). Within the non-underweight group, we found a significant difference between IL-8 inactive TB from latent TB (p<0,05). Mean level of IL-8 significantly higher in latent TB compared to active TB.

Discussion

Tuberculosis still becomes a health problem worldwide as the second most cause of mortality due to infection.[2] It is an air-borne disease from an inhaled droplet of nuclei consisted Mtb.[21] There is three possibilities of outcome after Mtb exposure. In some individuals, the bacteria can directly be eliminated, instantly after the exposure. The second possibility is granuloma formation; it is a strong natural and adaptive immune response by the host and resulting latent infection. While the third possibility would be a failure in adaptive immunity, resulting in primary infection, known as active TB.[22]

As mentioned before, our study involved 55 analysed samples within inclusion criteria, consisted of 20 samples of active pulmonary TB and 35 samples of latent TB. Characteristic showed 47,3% were males; age ranged from 13 to 72 yo, mean age was 43,3±16,4 yo. Distribution among the age group, 45,5% in group ≤ 40 yo and 54,5% within group >40 yo. According to nutritional status, we found 23,6% underweight subjects and 76,4% were non-underweight subjects.

Immune response as body defence against Mtb infection involving a humoral and cellular immune response. Humoral immune response mediated by antibody, non-protective, and mostly used in establishing the diagnosis. While the cellular immune response has more role in body defence against Mtb infection and involving more cytokines.[23]

Immune response to Mtb results from interactions of macrophage, T-cell, some cytokines and chemokines.[24] Recently, we are common to 2 types of cytokines that play a role in the immune response to Mtb infection, they are pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines. Some pro-inflammatory cytokines involved in the process are TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-12, IL-8, IL-15 and IFN- γ . Within anti-inflammatory cytokines group, there are IL-10, TGF- β and IL-4. There are also some known chemokines involved in the reaction to Mtb infection such as IL-8 and MCP-1.[8,9]

Interleukin-8 is a chemokine which plays an important role in attracting leukocytes into TB granuloma formation. As more and

more Mtb bacilli involved in infection, IL-8 level hypothetically would increase.[11] We found a significant difference between the level of IL-8 inactive TB group compared to the latent group. Mean IL-8 level were higher in latent TB (6636,1pg/mL) than inactive TB group (2760,5 pg/mL). Based on this result, we concluded that the inflammation process in latent TB was higher compared to active TB.

Our findings were almost similar to the results of Wu et al. study. In 2006, Wu et al. studied gene expression differences in active TB and latent TB. As a result, they found increasing of IL-8 gene expression in latent TB compared to active TB.[25]

Numbers of the previous study had assessed the IL-8 level in TB patients. Selvaraj et al., 2006, did an in vitro study on gene polymorphism about IL-8 production by MN cell in the peripheral circulation. They showed no significant differences between IL-8 level in active and non-active TB patients.[26] Siawaya in 2009 studied about secretion of various proinflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines in pulmonary TB patients. There were no significant differences between IL-8 plasma level in active and latent TB.[27] Another study by Phalane evaluated various cytokines level in saliva and serum of patients suspected as TB and non-TB and found that IL-8 level in saliva and serum of TB patients were higher than non-TB.[28]

Bacterial growth is associated with some factors.[12] Some factors would increase the possibility of becoming infected by TB, such as malnutrition, DM, and ageing. These factors cause a decrease in the immune system, making the person more vulnerable to get infected.[13-19]

To control the role of nutritional status, DM, and age, we performed multivariate analysis and found that IL-8 level was inseparable to nutritional status in both active and latent TB. Statistically, the role of both variables were 54,1%. There have been no other studies evaluating the role of factors like age, nutritional status and DM in the correlation between IL-8 level in active and latent TB.

The nutritional status reflects immune function against various types of infection. Thus, the presence of infection would also alter nutritional status. Malnutrition would affect the immune system related to complement and cytokines production.[13] The IL-8 level would be lower in malnutrition.[14] In contrary, the level would increase in obesity.[15,16]

The present study showed that in the underweight group, mean IL-8 level was higher in latent than in active TB. However, statistically, there were no significant differences between the IL-8 level in active and latent TB (p>0,05). Within the non-underweight group, there were substantial differences between IL-8 level in active and latent TB (p<0,05). Mean IL-8 level was significantly higher in latent TB compared to active TB. There has been a rising incidence of pulmonary TB in DM patients. This may due to the defect of immune cells function and distorted defence mechanism of the host. Though basic mechanism of this process has not fully understood.[29] Zozulinska et al., in 1999, found a rising IL-8 level in DM patients.[17] The result was similar to the study by Abou-Shousha et al., 2006; they reported a rising IL-8 level in DM patients.[18] On the contrary, experimental trial by Stalenhoef et al. found that there were no differences in human plasma cytokine production in TB patients with or without DM.[30] Ageing would cause a decrease in the immune system, so the elderly would become more vulnerable to get infected. Ageing would also lower macrophage capacity in inhibiting Mtb growth through inflammation responses.[19] Podkowka et al., 2002, reported that there were no significant

Table 4 Comparison of IL-8 level in active and latent TB based on Nutritional Status.

BMI	TB	n	Mean IL-8 level	SD	P
Underweight	Active TB	10	2066,6	3092,0	0,128
	Latent TB	3	7047,0	302,2	
Non-underweight	Active TB	10	3454,3	3364,6	0,018
	Latent TB	32	6597,6	1749,1	

differences between serum IL-8 level in elder subjects compared to younger ones, though seemed an increase of IL-8 level up to five times in elder subjects.[31] Limitations of our study were small sample and did not evaluate other factors that can alter IL-8 level, such as another infectious disease.

Conclusion

From this study, we concluded that in latent TB group, the IL-8 level was significantly higher than in the active TB group, and the difference was associated with nutritional status. We suggest doing a more advanced and large-scale study in the future. The level of IL-8 serum can be a potential adjunct test to distinct latent TB from active TB. However, we still need more advance study to evaluate other factors affecting IL-8 level.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in this study.

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